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Research Paper

Regional soil moisture prediction system based on Long Short-Term Memory network

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In the context of climate change, drought has been recognised as one of the most severe threats for agricultural production since absence of water is one of the most limiting factors for the growth of plants. In this study, a regional system for soil moisture prediction based on ERA5 climate reanalysis dataset, an open-source meteorological dataset issued by Copernicus Climate Change Service, was developed. It consisted of the relevant meteorological parameters for Serbia, during the period 2011–2020. Daily values of maximum and minimum air temperature, precipitation and vapour pressure deficit were used as features, and they were fed to recurrent neural network in order to predict volumetric soil moisture for three days ahead. A Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network was designed and trained at a regional scale using the data from the 2011–2016 period, at 28 locations that cover four major soil types. Validation was done on 2017–2018 data and LSTM was compared with a statistical forecasting technique and a classical machine learning approach. Evaluation was done with error measures commonly used in literature. The resulting network yielded the lowest errors and proved to have good generalisation properties. The system was tested from September 2019 to April 2020 using short-range weather forecasts of Yr service. It will present the cornerstone of the irrigation scheduling service in AgroSense.rs, the Serbian national platform for digital agriculture.

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1. Introduction

As a consequence of global warming, the frequency and intensity of extreme weather events have increased across many land systems in the world. This is particularly the case with heatwaves and droughts, especially in the drought-prone regions of the Mediterranean (Shukla et al., 2019). Weather patterns in Serbia are changing, thus affecting the air

temperature and precipitation regimes on the annual basis (Mimić, Mihailović, & Kapor, 2017). In the 21st century, warmer and drier conditions can be expected for all reference soil groups in Serbia, with an increase in mean annual soil temperature (up to 3.8 °C) and a decrease in mean annual soil moisture (up to 11.3%) (Mihailović et al., 2016). Additionally, a shift in climate zones is expected, which will influence the conditions during the growing season and the total

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Nomenclature	
API	Application Programming Interface
ARIMA	AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average
C3S	Copernicus Climate Change Service
D	vapour pressure deficit [hPa]
DSS	Decision-Support System
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-range Weather Forecasts
E	saturation vapour pressure [hPa]
ELU	exponential linear unit
ERA5	the fifth generation of ECMWF reanalysis
h_t	hidden state at time t
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
MAE	Mean Absolute Error
MASE	Mean Absolute Scaled Error
ReLU	rectified linear unit
RF	Random Forest
RNN	Recurrent Neural Network
SMAPE	Symmetric Mean Absolute Percentage Error
t	time
T	air temperature at 2 m [°C]
T_d	dewpoint temperature at 2 m [°C]
WMO	World Meteorological Organization
x_t	input at time t
Yr	joint service by the Norwegian Meteorological Institute and the Norwegian Broadcasting Corporation
θ_{sat}	volumetric soil moisture at saturation [$\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$]
θ_{fc}	field capacity [$\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$]
θ_{pwp}	permanent wilting point [$\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$]
θ_{paw}	plant available water [$\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$]

agricultural production in Serbia (Mihailović et al., 2015). The only way to overcome this challenging issue is through the use of irrigation, as a mitigation measure, or through revenue-protection insurance schemes.

Soil moisture is one of the essential climate variables according to World Meteorological Organization (WMO). It is very important in agriculture since it indicates the level of water available for crops, especially in dry conditions during the growing season (Mannocchi, Todisco, & Vergni, 2004). Insufficient amount of water in soil causes stress in crops and adversely affects plant growth and development (Ahmad, Malagoli, Wirtz, & Hell, 2016). Water uptake and evaporation occur predominately in topsoil, where the cumulative root length per unit of soil volume is the highest, and hence the path to water extraction and the hydraulic resistance are the lowest (Lobet, Couvreur, Meunier, Javaux, & Draye, 2014). Topsoil is the upper soil layer, usually reaching the depth of 13–25 cm, composed of organic matter, water, air and mineral particles (Marsh, 2010). Low water uptake by the plants happens when soil moisture content is close to permanent wilting point, and it depends on the soil texture as well (Fernández & Clothier, 2009). Thus, it is necessary to have reliable information on soil moisture content for timely and optimal irrigation scheduling. Soil moisture sensors can provide this

information, but unfortunately due to the high price of equipment, this technology is not available to a wider population of farmers.

Various applications of deep learning in agriculture and food production, including soil moisture prediction, have already been thoroughly examined (Kamilaris & Prenafeta-Boldú, 2018). Different neural network models, able to predict soil moisture dynamics with various input requirements, were presented and discussed in literature (Zheng et al., 2019). Comparison of machine learning techniques such as Multiple Linear Regression, Support Vector Machines and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) for prediction of soil moisture was performed on datasets collected from different online repositories (Prakash, Sharma, & Sahu, 2018). Adaptive Neuro Fuzzy Inference Systems, a technique that combines advantages from fuzzy logic and artificial neural networks, was used for making a decision-support system (DSS) for irrigation management in agriculture, based on weather variables and soil parameters from the sensors (Navarro-Hellín, Martínez-del Rincon, Domingo-Miguel, Soto-Valles, & Torres-Sánchez, 2016). Deep Belief Networks and Multi-Layer Perceptron were combined with macroscopic cellular automata in order to predict spatiotemporal probability of soil moisture content at the depth of 4 cm using irrigation data with many dynamic weather and soil variables (Song et al., 2016), where former showed better results, compared to the observations. Cai, Zheng, Zhang, Zhangzhong, and Xue (2019) discussed that selecting appropriate meteorological parameters as the input features of the model can significantly improve the accuracy of soil moisture prediction. In training a Deep Neural Network Regression model, the initial soil moisture was used as an input feature as well, and the obtained results were comparable to other models applied in Beijing, China (Cai et al., 2019). Feed-forward Neural Network and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) were tested for one-day-ahead predictions of soil moisture content, which was used for predictive irrigation scheduling (Adeyemi, Grove, Peets, Domun, & Norton, 2018). Daily values of air temperature, relative humidity, net radiation, wind speed, precipitation and volumetric soil moisture content were used to build the model which requires past and present meteorological inputs and past and present soil moisture content values. The downside of this methodology is the lag in predictions, as the changes in soil moisture are in line with the observations but shifted for one day. The authors commented as well that the predictive system should be extended to include rainfall forecasts. LSTM has been used for optimal irrigation prescription on an hourly basis, with training data collected from a precision irrigation study, and this system showed very good prediction capabilities (Jimenez, Ortiz, Bondesan, Morata, & Damianidis, 2019). However, the factor that hinders the scalability of this approach is the necessity of detailed hourly data from the sensors.

The objective of this study was to develop a deep learning system for prediction of soil moisture for three days ahead using open-source data, the most essential input variables and the weather forecast from Yr service including rainfall. This methodology does not require the data from soil sensors. LSTM network was trained to be robust for different soil types, thus applicable on a regional scale and not only for a

particular field. Since it is using globally available open-source data from ERA5, the system is scalable for other regions as well. Such system would help farmers make informed decisions about the time of irrigation, thus increasing their yields, reducing the risk of the production and saving the resources, specifically for the drought conditions.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Datasets

In order to achieve operability of the system throughout the region of interest, as well as to facilitate its potential scale-up, we relied on free, globally available data sources. In this way, a model trained on a number of points could be applied over a larger area with similar climate and soil characteristics. Although local calibration data may be required for scale-up over a region with different characteristics, the same methodology and system architecture that were developed for the initial region can be used in a novel environment. The two open data sources used in this study are Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S), for historical weather data, and Yr, for weather forecasts.

C3S provides information about the climate from ERA5, the fifth generation reanalysis of the global climate produced by European Centre for Medium-range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF). Reanalysis combines observations from across the world with modelled data to produce a complete and globally consistent dataset using the laws of physics and complex simulations. Data assimilation is done with horizontal resolution of $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ (approximately 25 km at mid-latitudes) and hourly data are produced (C3S, 2017). There are four soil layers in ERA5, segregated by the depth: the first (0–7 cm), second (7–28 cm), third (28–100 cm) and fourth (100–289 cm).

Based on the ERA5 literature, for the vegetation type that represents crops from mixed farming, 21% of the root system is in the first layer, 41% is in the second layer (the largest part), 31% is in the third layer, while only 4% is in the fourth layer (ECMWF, 2016), and thus the second layer is of the highest interest in agriculture. Soil types are classified based on soil texture as follows: 1 – coarse, 2 – medium, 3 – medium fine, 4 – fine. Characteristic values of volumetric soil moisture for different textures are given in Table 1.

Using Climate Data Store Application Programming Interface (API), we extracted air temperature at 2 m, dewpoint temperature at 2 m, precipitation and volumetric soil moisture content in the second layer (7–28 cm), for the period

2011–2020, at the location of 28 meteorological stations belonging to the official observing network in Serbia (Table 2). In this study, the daily values of meteorological variables, i.e., maximum and minimum 2 m temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$), total precipitation (mm), vapour pressure deficit (hPa) and average volumetric soil moisture content in the second layer ($\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$) were used. Vapour pressure deficit was calculated as $D = E(T) - E(T_d)$ where E stands for the saturation vapour pressure following Magnus's formula (Junzeng, Qi, Shizhang, & Yanmei, 2012), T is the average temperature and T_d average dewpoint temperature. This variable reflects the rate of evapotranspiration, and the higher values force the plant to draw more water from the soil.

Three-day weather forecasts from Yr service (www.yr.no) are also freely available and accessible through an API. These include forecasts of precipitation, temperature at 2 m and dewpoint temperature at 2 m, at a spatial resolution of 2 km, and an hourly temporal resolution. For the purpose of testing the developed network, forecast data were collected from September 2019 until April 2020, at the locations of 28 meteorological stations described above.

2.2. Recurrent neural networks

RNNs are widely used for time series prediction, handwriting recognition, natural language processing and speech recognition, since they show excellent performance in “sequence-to-sequence” modelling (Goodfellow, Bengio, & Courville, 2016). RNNs are also known as neural networks with memory because they are capable of learning dependencies along sequences and produce output taking into consideration the previous output, or what they learned from the input in the previous time step (Burkov, 2019). In other words, RNNs model dynamical systems where x_t represents the input at time t and h_t , h_{t-1} represent hidden states at time t , $t-1$, respectively (Chen, 2016). Function F is used for nonlinear mapping between consecutive time steps, as described in Eq. (1)

$$h_t = F(h_{t-1}, x_t) \quad (1)$$

RNNs typically have vanishing gradient problem, i.e., weights are becoming irreversibly smaller in every iteration, which slows down or completely stops the training. For this reason, LSTM networks have been developed. With a memory cell and the gates that control which information passes in and passes out, LSTM prevents backpropagation from drastically decreasing the weight changes during training and keeps the constant error flow. This architecture lets LSTM to learn longer-term dependencies, the network can deal with unlimited number of states, and it generalises well (Hochreiter & Schmidhuber, 1997).

In this study, the hyperopt technique (Bergstra, Yamins, & Cox, 2013) was used on validation dataset to determine the optimal hyper-parameters in the experiments. The following parameter grid was searched: number of neurons ranged from 10 to 60, number of epochs ranged from 40 to 100, batch size ranged from 128 to 512, dropout rate ranged from 0.1 to 0.5, recurrent dropout rate ranged from 0.1 to 0.5, while the choice for the activation function was between hyperbolic tangent, rectified linear unit (ReLU) and exponential linear unit (ELU).

Table 1 – Values of soil moisture at saturation (θ_{sat}), field capacity (θ_{fc}), permanent wilting point (θ_{pwp}) and plant available water (θ_{paw}), for different soil texture (van Genuchten, 1980).

Texture	θ_{sat}	θ_{fc}	θ_{pwp}	θ_{paw}
Coarse	0.403	0.244	0.059	0.185
Medium	0.439	0.347	0.151	0.196
Medium-Fine	0.430	0.383	0.133	0.251
Fine	0.520	0.448	0.279	0.170

Table 2 – Location of stations in Serbia used in the study with given soil type.

Station	Code	Latitude (°)	Longitude (°)	Altitude (m)	Soil type
Palic	S1	46.10	19.77	102	1
Sombor	S2	45.77	19.15	88	2
Novi Sad	S3	45.33	19.85	84	1
Zrenjanin	S4	45.37	20.42	80	2
Kikinda	S5	45.85	20.47	81	3
Banatski Karlovac	S6	45.05	21.03	100	3
Loznica	S7	44.55	19.23	121	2
Sremska Mitrovica	S8	45.10	19.55	82	2
Valjevo	S9	44.32	19.92	176	2
Beograd	S10	44.80	20.47	132	2
Kragujevac	S11	44.03	20.93	185	2
Smederevska Palanka	S12	44.37	20.95	121	2
Veliko Gradiste	S13	44.75	21.52	82	2
Crni Vrh	S14	44.12	21.95	1037	4
Negotin	S15	44.23	22.55	42	4
Zlatibor	S16	43.73	19.72	1028	2
Sjenica	S17	43.28	20.00	1038	2
Pozega	S18	43.85	20.03	310	2
Kraljevo	S19	43.70	20.70	215	2
Kopaonik	S20	43.28	20.80	1710	2
Kursumljaja	S21	43.13	21.27	384	4
Krusevac	S22	43.57	21.35	166	2
Cuprija	S23	43.93	21.38	123	2
Nis	S24	43.33	21.90	202	2
Leskovac	S25	42.98	21.95	230	2
Zajecar	S26	43.88	22.30	144	4
Dimitrovgrad	S27	43.02	22.75	450	2
Vranje	S28	42.55	21.92	432	2

After 30 iterations the optimal parameters were found. A stacked LSTM with 4 layers and 40 neurons in each layer followed by a dense layer with 3 neurons (Fig. 1) was built. For the activation function the hyperbolic tangent was used while for weight initialisation the Xavier normal initialiser was used (Glorot & Bengio, 2010). During the training period, the optimal hyper-parameters were used, i.e., batch size was 128, dropout regularisation with the rate of 0.12, while the recurrent dropout rate was 0.25. This means that in each iteration some fraction of neurons were randomly deactivated, which helped to avoid overfitting and maintain a similar convergence rate of both training and validation errors over time. Training and validation procedure was done through 60 epochs with dropout and Adam optimiser, while mean absolute error (MAE) was selected as the loss function. The LSTM network was trained with meteorological data and prediction of soil moisture was done for three days ahead.

Fig. 1 – Structure of a recurrent neural network used in the study.

2.3. Computational setup

The study was implemented using Python and open-source libraries, including Keras library, commonly used for neural networks on top of TensorFlow, an end-to-end open-source machine learning platform. The network was compared to ARIMA (AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average), a traditional statistical forecasting technique (Hewamalage, Bergmeir, & Bandara, 2021) and Random Forest (RF) (Breiman, 2001), a classical machine learning technique, which has been widely used in water science applications recently (Tyralis, Papacharalampous, & Langousis, 2019).

All the models were trained for the period 2011–2016 and applied with the time step of three days. To build the models, daily values of meteorological variables from ERA5 were used. ARIMA was trained on individual time series of soil moisture, for each meteorological station separately. For this reason, the results of ARIMA predictions were averaged across all time series and a single value was obtained for each error metric. RF and LSTM used maximum and minimum 2 m temperature, total precipitation and vapour pressure deficit as the input data. Initially 60 input days were selected, which is taken from the literature (van den Hurk et al., 2012), although the performance of the network was tested with shorter time period of 45, 30 and 15 days. RF and LSTM were trained across the time series from all 28 meteorological stations jointly, whereas RF used the input data as a single vector while LSTM used four different time series (Fig. 2). Validation was done for the period 2017–2018 and, according to its mode of operation, the statistical model was retrained during the runtime, i.e.,

along the time series. The year 2017 in Serbia was warm and dry, with the summer drier than normal compared to the reference period 1981–2010 (HIDMET, 2018), which resulted in agricultural drought. The year 2018 was marked by several climatological records in Serbia: the warmest year since the record-keeping began (1951), the warmest spring and the warmest April, while on the other hand, the summer was wetter than normal, with a lot of precipitation in June and July (HIDMET, 2019). In order to test the predictive model with Yr weather forecast, instead of only the ERA5 data, a separate dataset that comprised of the ERA5 historical records and the Yr's three-day forecasts from September 2019 to April 2020 (Fig. 2) was formed. The results of the models were evaluated using MASE (Mean Absolute Scaled Error), SMAPE (Symmetric Mean Absolute Percentage Error) and MAE, metrics commonly used in the forecasting literature (Armstrong, 2001; Hewamalage et al., 2021; Hyndman & Koehler, 2006). Error metrics are given with the following equations:

$$MASE = \frac{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |M_i - O_i|}{\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=2}^n |O_i - O_{i-1}|} \quad (2)$$

$$SMAPE = \frac{100\%}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{|M_i - O_i|}{(|M_i| + |O_i|)/2} \quad (3)$$

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |M_i - O_i| \quad (4)$$

where M stands for modelled and O for observed values (here referring to ERA5 data), n represents the number of samples, i refers to a specific sample, while the denominator in Eq. (2) is the MAE of the one-step “naïve forecast method”, which uses the actual value from the prior period as the forecast. MASE and SMAPE are dimensionless metrics while MAE has the same unit as considered variable, which is soil moisture in this case, given in $m^3 m^{-3}$.

3. Results

An experiment was performed to train the LSTM model with different number of input days ranging from 15 to 60, with a 15-day step, in order to predict soil moisture three days ahead. The aim of the experiment was to examine if it is possible to

Table 3 – Error measures averaged for all the stations (with standard deviation in round brackets) obtained for different number of input days used for training LSTM.

Input days	MASE	SMAPE	MAE
60	3.99 (1.28)	19.76 (9.10)	0.021 (0.006)
45	4.19 (1.35)	20.39 (8.10)	0.024 (0.006)
30	4.78 (1.35)	22.19 (8.80)	0.024 (0.006)
15	5.70 (1.49)	24.85 (9.02)	0.029 (0.006)

decrease the time window of input data without compromising the quality of the prediction. However, validation showed that as the time window decreased, the error measures increased (Table 3). Thus, the initially selected value of 60 input days was opted. The same number of input days was used for training RF model as well.

The performance of the LSTM model was compared to RF and ARIMA, which were used as a benchmark and LSTM expressed the lowest error values (Table 4), with SMAPE less than 20%. Being a univariate method in which one model is built for each time series ARIMA has limited scaling potential and requires frequent retraining (Hewamalage et al., 2021). Theoretically, this univariate approach could be used, but only for the regular grid points of ERA5, although the fact that ERA5 data are available only with a delay of two months is making the traditional approach incapable for practical applications. On the other hand, the LSTM and RF models were trained across all time series and one general model was built in both cases, that could cover the whole region of interest. This model can thus be used at any location in Serbia with reliable weather data. However, RF as a method does not consider time sequence of the features, whereby the dynamics of atmospheric conditions is of great importance for soil moisture regimes, making LSTM a physically more realistic model.

To discuss the significance of the error measures obtained for the different models, the range of soil moisture values given in Table 1 and shown in Fig. 3 has to be considered. For all the soil types, the range between minimum and maximum soil moisture is around $0.3 m^3 m^{-3}$, although soils with coarse and medium texture have lower minimum values reaching $0.05 m^3 m^{-3}$ while soils with fine texture have higher minimum values. Since MAE has the unit of $m^3 m^{-3}$, the same as soil moisture, it is the most suitable for comparison between

Fig. 2 – Schematic diagram of the input data structure for all the models, where m_a is the number of days in soil moisture time series used in ARIMA, while m is the number of input days and n represents four input variables used in RF and LSTM.

Table 4 – Error measures averaged for all the stations (with standard deviation in round brackets) obtained for different prediction methods on the validation dataset.

Method	MASE	SMAPE	MAE
ARIMA	10.72 (2.85)	123.49 (16.64)	0.055 (0.009)
RF	5.93 (1.42)	25.88 (8.76)	0.031 (0.005)
LSTM	3.99 (1.28)	19.76 (9.10)	0.021 (0.006)

the models. Average MAE for ARIMA is 0.055 (almost 20% of the range), for RF it is 0.031 (above 10% of the range) while for LSTM it is 0.021 (7% of the range), showing much better performance of LSTM when compared to ARIMA and slightly better performance when compared to RF, however this difference can be essential in the case of dry conditions, when soil moisture values are reaching the wilting point.

In this study, the predominant soil type had medium soil texture and 20 stations out of 28 belonged to the group 2 (Table 2). Nevertheless, for this soil type median of soil moisture varied a lot in the training dataset and the outliers with low values were present at five stations, which was particularly evident at station S9 (Fig. 3). Error measures for all the stations in Serbia are presented in Table 5. The highest MASE error was obtained for station S9 where the learning process of LSTM was clearly affected by the outliers. Another high error was obtained for station S11, whereby both stations belong to soil type with medium texture. For all other stations, the values of MASE were less than six and for some stations MASE was almost one. The range of MAE values was between 0.010 and 0.031, showing that LSTM was able to learn soil moisture dynamics for all the soil types at various altitudes, thus verifying the generalisation capability of the network.

The predictive system was tested from September 2019 until April 2020, and the results are presented in Table 6 and partially in Fig. 4. Soil moisture predictions using Yr's three-day forecasts (LSTM + Yr) and predictions with ERA5 data (LSTM) were compared to original reanalysis data of soil

moisture (ERA5). Error measures were quite similar in both cases, having reasonably low values. The selected results are depicting soil moisture at four stations which belong to different soil types (Fig. 4), where S3 is 1, S7 is 2, S5 is 3 and S14 is 4 (Table 2). Visual inspection shows that the alignment between the values is notable, even though there are some “false” spikes in soil moisture when using Yr forecast due to the uncertainty coming from the weather forecast itself, especially at the end of the prognostic period.

4. Discussion

The experts suggested that a national drought policy should be directed toward reducing the risk by raising the awareness with reliable information (Wilhite, 2011). Timely monitoring of the agricultural drought is extremely important for developing an early warning system which can minimise the losses due to drought (Boken, 2005). Satellite observations of surface soil moisture along with the calculated vegetation and water indices can be used in an effective way for monitoring dry conditions in the fields with proper spatial resolution (Chandrasekar, Sessa Sai, Roy, & Dwevedi, 2010), although the temporal resolution of five or more days and the presence of cloud cover can be a limiting factor. In this study, a data-driven system for calculation of soil moisture on a regional scale using open-source weather data was developed, which is able to provide timely information regardless of the atmospheric conditions. Shukla, McNally, Husak, and Funk (2014) developed a forecast system that simulates soil moisture scenarios using hydrological model which was run with seasonal climate scenarios for the upcoming growing season. The purpose of that system was to create an agricultural outlook of the drought in food-insecure regions of the developing world, although it was clearly affected by the uncertainty of seasonal forecasts (Doblas-Reyes et al., 2009). For that reason, the focus was on short-range weather forecasts, which have the lowest

Fig. 3 – Boxplot statistics of soil moisture from training dataset, for all the stations, grouped by the soil type.

Table 5 – Error measures for all the stations in Serbia obtained with the LSTM model on the validation dataset.

Station code	MASE	SMAPE	MAE
S1	4.57	32.91	0.026
S2	4.74	30.97	0.029
S3	4.76	28.72	0.024
S4	5.33	29.34	0.023
S5	3.86	24.33	0.022
S6	3.97	33.16	0.025
S7	2.01	9.20	0.012
S8	5.11	25.85	0.022
S9	6.95	21.30	0.031
S10	3.27	22.37	0.019
S11	6.36	19.49	0.027
S12	3.09	13.15	0.019
S13	4.95	32.46	0.030
S14	4.46	23.92	0.027
S15	5.48	33.01	0.025
S16	1.55	5.74	0.011
S17	4.04	11.79	0.017
S18	1.56	5.83	0.010
S19	3.06	10.87	0.015
S20	3.45	10.32	0.014
S21	4.02	23.13	0.027
S22	2.82	9.49	0.014
S23	3.11	10.29	0.014
S24	3.65	15.03	0.016
S25	2.96	11.29	0.014
S26	4.53	27.21	0.025
S27	3.74	17.57	0.022
S28	4.24	14.59	0.017

Table 6 – Error measures averaged across all the stations (with standard deviation in round brackets) obtained for ERA5 test dataset and Yr weather forecasts.

	MASE	SMAPE	MAE
LSTM	3.31 (1.22)	16.35 (6.76)	0.018 (0.007)
LSTM + Yr	3.48 (1.18)	16.56 (6.33)	0.019 (0.006)

level of uncertainty, when considering different prognostic periods. Matei, Rusu, Petrovan, and Mihauc (2017) developed a data mining system used for predicting soil moisture in some agricultural spots in Romania. It was built by using the data from 10 weather stations that measured air temperature, precipitation, soil temperatures at three depths and soil moisture at 10 cm depth. They tested several machine learning models and the best one had accuracy 74.36%. The current work obtained average MAE of $0.019 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}$ while predicting soil moisture with LSTM using Yr weather forecasts (Table 6), which is around 6% of the range between minimum and maximum values of soil moisture, being approximately $0.3 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}$ (Fig. 3).

The proposed methodology will become operational through installation of 500 automatic weather stations across the fields in Serbia and further integration into AgroSense, the national platform for digital agriculture (www.agrosense.rs). The data will be used with the LSTM model to calculate the current level of soil moisture and, along with the weather forecast, to predict the future states. This methodology will be

Fig. 4 – Soil moisture predictions with LSMT compared to ERA5 data for stations with different soil type: a) S3, b) S7, c) S5 and d) S14.

the cornerstone of the AgroSense service for irrigation scheduling, as an alarm for warning farmers to react in the case of risk of soil moisture declining to the permanent wilting point.

5. Conclusions

In this study a LSTM network was developed to predict daily values of soil moisture in the second soil layer, for three days ahead. The input parameters used were the daily values of maximum and minimum air temperature, precipitation and vapour pressure deficit. For this purpose, an open-source data from ERA5 reanalysis for Serbia were used. Validation was performed for 2017 which had a dry summer and 2018 which had a wet summer. The overall performance of the network was characterised with much lower values of errors, when compared to ARIMA, a statistical forecasting technique, and Random Forest, a classical machine learning algorithm, thus verifying the prediction capabilities of the network for all soil types at various altitudes. The system was tested with Yr weather forecast and the predictions were in line with the ERA5 reanalysis data, proving the system's potential to be used by the farmers as an irrigation scheduling service, specifically for the drought conditions.

Author contributions

Nemanja Filipović: Formal analysis, Investigation, Validation, Visualisation; Sanja Brdar: Methodology, Writing - review & editing; Gordan Mimić: Conceptualization, Writing - original draft; Oskar Marko: Funding acquisition, Writing - review & editing; Vladimir Crnojević: Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

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